

VelCrys: Interactive web-based application to compute acoustic wave velocity in crystals and its magnetic corrections

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a web-based interactive tool called VelCrys that allows to compute and plot the group velocity of the acoustic waves in crystals, as well as to account for the effects of an external magnetic field on sound. The group velocity is obtained by calculating Christoffel matrix elements and their partial derivatives with respect to the phase velocity direction, and inserting them into an analytical expression for the group velocity. The effect of that external magnetic field is computed through the induced effective corrections to the elastic tensor which depend on the magnetic susceptibility tensor and the magnetoelastic constants. We apply it to dry sandstone, cubic CoPt and hcp Co to show some of the program's features. In the analysis of the magnetic field effects, we find complex landscapes of fractional change in group velocity as a function of ray direction, as well as a field dependence consistent with the Simon effect.

Metadata

Nr.	Code metadata description	Metadata
C1	Current code version	1.0
C2	Permanent link to code/repository used for this code version	https://github.com/pnieves2019/VelCrys
C3	Permanent link to Reproducible Capsule	–
C4	Legal Code License	BSD 3-Clause License
C5	Code versioning system used	git
C6	Software code languages, tools, and services used	Python3
C7	Compilation requirements, operating environments & dependencies	Linux, Windows
C8	If available Link to developer documentation/manual	https://github.com/pnieves2019/VelCrys
C9	Support email for questions	nievespablo@uniovi.es

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1. Motivation and significance

The characterization of wave velocity is particularly useful in many fields like geophysics [1–5], communication technology [6] or biosensors [7]. The way acoustic waves propagate in crystals can be highly anisotropic, and thus it is different and more complicated than in isotropic media [8]. Given the phase velocity direction, one finds three possible modes for an acoustic wave: one quasi-compressional wave (qP) and two quasi-shear waves (qS1 and qS2) [1]. Over the last five decades, great efforts have been made to develop theoretical techniques to compute wave velocity for a general anisotropic media [1,9–12]. For instance, Zhou et al. [12] proposed the eigenvalue and eigenvector methods to calculate the group velocity. A more manageable approach has been recently proposed by Wang et al. [1] based on analytical formulas for group velocity, which can address the singular points and multivalued problems of the qS wave.

Magnetic effects on wave velocity in magnetostrictive materials are interesting from a fundamental and technological point of view [13–16]. The effect of a magnetic field on wave velocity was originally discovered by Simon in 1958 (Simon effect) [13,15–17]. Additionally, other magnetic effects have been identified such as isotropic exchange effects [18], anisotropic morphic effects [13,19,20], rotational-magnetostrictive effects [13,14], and Δs -effect [14], which have been experimentally observed in ultrasonic elastic waves [14–16,21–27]. In 1979, a comprehensive theoretical description of these effects was reported by Rouchy et al. for cubic crystals [13]. Later, Rinaldi and Turilli showed that linear magnetic effects on wave velocity can be equivalently taken into account as effective corrections to the elastic constants [28]. In general, the theoretical analysis of magnetic effects on wave velocity is difficult, and typically is only studied in simplified cases such as along high symmetry crystallographic directions in cubic crystals [13,14]. Therefore, computational tools that allow to calculate such effects for any arbitrary wave and field directions could be highly desirable, and may be exploited in the research of novel magneto-acoustic phenomena such as acoustic spin pumping [29], magnetization switching induced by sound waves [30–37] and picosecond ultrasonics [38].

Currently, advanced visualization tools in databases are greatly helping to accelerate the design of new materials in different areas of condensed matter physics [39–41]. For example, ELATE is an online user-friendly interface that has been implemented to analyze the elastic tensor and visualize anisotropic mechanical properties [42]. Similarly, MAELASviewer was developed to visualize anisotropic magnetostrictive properties [43–45]. In this work, we present VelCrys a web-based interactive tool that performs further post-processing of the elastic tensor in order to compute and plot the sound velocity of the three kinds of acoustic waves (qP, qS1, and qS2) for any crystal symmetry based on the analytical formulas derived by Wang et al. [1]. Additionally, it can also calculate the effective magnetic corrections to the elastic tensor using the approach by Rinaldi and Turilli [28], as well as the corresponding fractional change in sound velocity via Wang et al. method [1]. We show that this approach may provide a practical way to efficiently compute the fractional change in group velocity due to linear magnetic effects for arbitrary wave propagation direction and applied magnetic field. Hence, it may facilitate the analysis of this phenomenon beyond the cases with wave propagation and magnetic field directions along high symmetry crystallographic directions, that have been studied so far, as well as for crystals with symmetry lower than cubic [13,15,18,22].

2. Software description

VelCrys is a software package for calculation and visualization of group velocity of acoustic waves in crystals. The code is developed in the Python 3 programming language. The online application is currently available at <http://www.md-esp.eu/velcrys/>, while the open source

Python module is available at GitHub repository [46]. VelCrys can be also used offline by executing the Python module [46].

2.1. Software architecture

VelCrys contains two components: (i) a Graphical User Interface (GUI) and (ii) display module. VelCrys GUI is created with Dash which is an efficient Python framework for building web applications [47]. Dash uses Flask as the web framework [48]. The display module generates 3D surfaces using the Python open source graphing library Plotly [49]. We also make use of NumPy library for some mathematical operations.

2.2. Software functionalities

The calculation of group velocity \mathbf{v} for any crystal symmetry is performed in VelCrys by calculating Christoffel matrix elements (Γ), their partial derivatives with respect to the phase velocity direction, and inserting them into analytical expression for group velocity derived by Wang et al. [1]

$$v_l(C_{ij}) = \frac{\partial c}{\partial n_l} = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial k_l}, \quad l = x, y, z \quad (1)$$

where C_{ij} is the elastic tensor, $c = \omega/k$ is the phase velocity, \mathbf{k} is the wavevector, ω is the angular frequency, and $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{k}/k$ is the unit vector of phase velocity direction (ray direction).

The effective magnetic corrections (ΔC_{ij}) to the elastic tensor are obtained through the formulas derived by Rinaldi and Turilli, which have the form [28]

$$\Delta C_{ij} = \frac{1}{M_s^2} b_{pqt} b_{rsj} \alpha_p \alpha_r \chi_{qs}, \quad (2)$$

where b are magnetoelastic constants, M_s is the saturation magnetization, α is the direction cosine of magnetization at equilibrium, and χ is the susceptibility tensor, see Ref. [28] for details about subscript indexes. The corresponding fractional change in group velocity due to magnetic effects $(v - v_0)/v_0$ is obtained by computing Wang et al. formulas [1] using the elastic tensor including effective magnetic corrections ($C_{ij} + \Delta C_{ij}$), that leads to v , and elastic tensor without effective magnetic corrections (C_{ij}) which gives v_0 , that is

$$\frac{v - v_0}{v_0} = \frac{v(C_{ij} + \Delta C_{ij}) - v(C_{ij})}{v(C_{ij})}. \quad (3)$$

This option is currently supported only for cubic I (point groups 432, $\bar{4}3m$, $m\bar{3}m$, space group numbers from 207 up to 230), and hexagonal I (point groups 6 mm , 622, $\bar{6}2m$, 6/ mmm , space group numbers from 177 up to 194) symmetries [28]. As for the original work in Ref. [28], we include in the total energy the following terms

$$E = E_{el} + E_{me} + E_K + E_Z. \quad (4)$$

where E_{el} is the elastic energy, E_{me} is the magnetoelastic energy, E_K is the anisotropy energy and E_Z is the Zeeman energy. Additional terms not included here, like demagnetizing energy and exchange stiffness, could also influence the fractional change in group velocity at low applied magnetic fields [50]. Similarly, Rinaldi and Turilli's expressions do not include higher order corrections like morphic and rotational-magnetostrictive effects [18]. The limitations arising from the lack of these terms are discussed in Section 3.2.

3. Illustrative examples

In this section, we perform some tests on the methodology implemented in VelCrys.

Table 1
Elastic constants ($C_{ij} = C_{ji}$) of dry sandstone [1].

C_{ij}	(GPa)								
C_{11}	10.3	C_{12}	0.9	C_{13}	1.3	C_{14}	1.4	C_{15}	1.1
		C_{22}	10.6	C_{23}	2.1	C_{24}	0.2	C_{25}	-0.2
				C_{33}	14.1	C_{34}	0.0	C_{35}	-0.5
						C_{44}	5.1	C_{45}	0.0
								C_{55}	6.0
								C_{56}	0.0
								C_{66}	4.9

Fig. 1. Isoline of the group velocity ($v = 2.6$ km/s) of the qP wave for dry sandstone with varied ray angle (ϕ, θ) obtained with VelCrys (blue squares), program V4GAM (green disks) [53] and by Wang et al. [1] (black triangles).

3.1. Dry sandstone

Sandstone is a sedimentary rock widely distributed on planet Earth mostly composed of sand-sized minerals or rock grains cemented by siliceous, argillaceous, and/or calcareous materials [51]. Its mechanical properties depend highly upon the degree of cementation and grain composition [51] which are affected by temperature and burial history [51,52]. In this first example, we verify the correct implementation in VelCrys of Wang et al. [1,53] methodology by computing the group velocity of complex dry sandstone and comparing it with their results [1]. The elastic constants of this material are shown in Table 1, while the mass density is $\rho = 2080$ kg/m³ at room temperature [1]. In Fig. 1, we compare the group velocity for a qP wave obtained with VelCrys and reported by Wang et al. [1], finding good agreement. Here, we also reproduced these results with the Fortran program Velocity4GeneralAnisotropicMedium (V4GAM) available in the GitHub repository [53]. A 3D plot generated with VelCrys is shown in Fig. 2, where one can see the group velocity landscape of the qP wave as a function of the ray direction (phase velocity direction), again consistent with Ref. [1].

3.2. Co-Pt alloy

Co-Pt (and Fe-Pt) are very interesting alloys since supported nanostructures of these alloys present a direct link between atomic arrangements and magnetic behavior. Additionally, both alloys are today model systems in the field of nanoalloys, due to the diversity of atomic arrangements present either in bulk state or specific to the nanoscale (disordered fcc structures, chemically ordered L1₀, L1₂, core-shell, five-fold structures – icosahedral or decahedral, etc). Importantly, Co-Pt alloys that can be used as permanent magnet materials are found around the equiatomic composition where the disordered A1 (fcc) phase

Fig. 2. Group velocity landscape as a function of the ray direction (phase velocity direction) $\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{k}/k = (\sin \theta \cos \phi, \sin \theta \sin \phi, \cos \theta)$ of the qP wave for dry sandstone generated with VelCrys. The color of the surface corresponds to the magnitude of group velocity $|v|$.

transforms into the ordered L1₀ phase [56]. Here, we further test VelCrys' capabilities by evaluating magnetic corrections to group velocity for cubic single crystals of disordered equiatomic Co-Pt alloy, and comparing the results with theory and experiment [14,54]. The fractional change in group velocity $(v - v_0)/v_0$ due to magnetic effects may be written as [13,18]

$$\frac{v - v_0}{v_0} = \frac{F - F_0}{F_0} + \frac{l - l_0}{l_0}, \quad (5)$$

where F is the frequency of sound wave measured in ultrasound experiments (for instance, by the pulse echo method [14,22]) and l is the length in the direction of wave propagation. The fractional change of frequency could be further splitted into [13–16,18]

$$\frac{F - F_0}{F_0} = G(m) + R(\lambda) + S(H) + \Delta, \quad (6)$$

where $G(m)$ accounts for a higher order correction arising from the morphic coefficients m , $R(\lambda)$ comes from rotational and magnetostrictive effects, $S(H)$ describes the Simon effect that depends on the external magnetic field \mathbf{H} [17], and Δ corresponds to other possible effects like the Δs -effect associated to domain walls displacement in the low magnetic field regime [14]. The anisotropic part of the fractional change in length reads [15,18]

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{l - l_0}{l_0} \right|_{\beta}^{\alpha} &= \lambda^{\gamma,2} \left(\alpha_x^2 \beta_x^2 + \alpha_y^2 \beta_y^2 + \alpha_z^2 \beta_z^2 - \frac{1}{3} \right) \\ &+ 2\lambda^{\epsilon,2} (\alpha_x \alpha_y \beta_x \beta_y + \alpha_y \alpha_z \beta_y \beta_z + \alpha_x \alpha_z \beta_x \beta_z), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where α is the direction cosine of magnetization, β is the normalized vector along the measuring length direction, and $\lambda^{\gamma,2} = 3\lambda_{100}/2$ and $\lambda^{\epsilon,2} = 3\lambda_{111}/2$ are the magnetostrictive coefficients. In this example, we consider longitudinal (qP) and transverse (qS) elastic waves propagating along the crystallographic direction [001] ($\mathbf{k} \parallel [001]$), where the magnetic field is applied either along $\mathbf{H} \parallel [001]$ or $\mathbf{H} \parallel [100]$. In Table 3, we present the theoretical expression for each magnetic contribution ($G(m)$, $R(\lambda)$, $S(H)$ and $(l - l_0)/l_0$) to the fractional change in group velocity $(v - v_0)/v_0$ in a cubic crystal [13,14,18] for these cases. A comparison between experiment, theory and VelCrys is shown in Figs. 3 and 4, finding consistent results. In function $G(m)$, we use experimental values of the morphic coefficients $m_1^{\gamma,2} = -0.15$ GPa, and $m_3^{\gamma,2} = 0.77$ GPa, while for the other properties we use the experimental values shown in Table 2 [14]. The fractional change in frequency F is indirectly obtained in VelCrys

Fig. 3. Fractional change in ultrasound frequency for a longitudinal wave (qP) under an applied magnetic field parallel or perpendicular to the wave propagation vector for cubic single crystals of disordered Co-Pt alloy. Red stars and orange diamonds show experimental data from Ref. [14] for the cases $H \parallel [001]$ and $H \parallel [100]$, respectively. Red solid and orange dashed lines stand for the theoretical values obtained from Eq. (6) and Table 3. Open blue squares and solid pink circles give the values derived from the computed fractional change in group velocity $(v - v_0)/v_0$ by VelCrys via Eq. (5). We added the experimentally observed Δs -effect at saturated state ($\Delta^{sat} = 0.00435$) both in the theoretical values and VelCrys data.

Fig. 4. Fractional change in ultrasound frequency for a transverse wave (qS1) under an applied magnetic field parallel or perpendicular to the wave propagation vector for cubic single crystals of disordered equiatomic Co-Pt alloy. Red stars and orange diamonds show experimental data from Ref. [14] for the cases $H \parallel [100]$ and $H \parallel [001]$, respectively. Red solid and orange dashed lines stand for the theoretical values obtained from Eq. (6) and Table 3. Open blue squares and solid pink circles give the values derived from the computed fractional change in group velocity $(v - v_0)/v_0$ by VelCrys via Eq. (5). We added the experimentally observed Δs -effect at saturated state ($\Delta^{sat} = 0.00435$) both in the theoretical values and VelCrys data.

by using the calculated fractional change in group velocity in Eq. (5). Here, the experimentally observed Δs -effect, about $\Delta = 0.00435$ at the saturated state [14], is included both in theory and VelCrys. For the sake of simplicity, the demagnetizing field was not included ($H_D = 0$) in the Simon effect $S(H)$. Note that VelCrys gives the same value for the cases with $H \parallel k$ and $H \perp k$, failing to reproduce the small observed shift δ between both cases. In the case of transverse waves (Fig. 4), this discrepancy is due to the fact that Rinaldi and Turilli's work [28] is based

Table 2

Experimental elastic constants (C_{ij}), anisotropic magnetoelastic constants (b), anisotropic magnetostrictive coefficients (λ), magnetocrystalline anisotropy constant (K_1), saturation magnetization (M_s), exchange stiffness (A) and mass density (ρ) for cubic single crystals of disordered equiatomic Co-Pt alloy at room temperature [14,54,55].

C_{ij}	(GPa)	b	(MPa)	λ	($\times 10^{-6}$)	K_1	(kJ/m ³)	$\mu_0 M_s$	(T)	A	(pJ/m)	ρ	(kg/m ³)
C_{11}	289.7	b_1	-35	λ_{100}	210	-40		0.942		10		16,696.7	
C_{12}	178.5	b_2	11.9	λ_{111}	-53								
C_{44}	124.1												

Table 3

Theoretical expression for each magnetic contribution to fractional change in group velocity $(v - v_0)/v_0$ in a cubic crystal [13,14,18]. Here, u corresponds to the displacement vector, while other quantities are defined in the main text.

$k \parallel$	$u \parallel$	$H \parallel$	$G(m)$	$R(\lambda)$	$S(H)$	$(l - l_0)/l_0$	Wave
[001]	[001]	[001]	$\frac{2m_1^2}{3C_{11}^2}$	0	0	λ_{100}	qP
[001]	[001]	[100]	$-\frac{m_1^2}{3C_{11}^2}$	0	0	$-\frac{\lambda_{100}}{2}$	qP
[001]	[100]	[001]	$-\frac{m_1^2}{12C_{44}^2}$	$\frac{3}{2}(\lambda_{111} - \lambda_{100})$	$-\frac{(b_2)^2}{2C_{44}\mu_0 M_s (H + H_D + H_K)}$	λ_{100}	qS1
[001]	[100]	[100]	$-\frac{m_1^2}{12C_{44}^2}$	$\frac{3}{2}(\lambda_{100} - \lambda_{111})$	$-\frac{(b_2)^2}{2C_{44}\mu_0 M_s (H + H_s + H_D + H_K)}$	$-\frac{\lambda_{100}}{2}$	qS1

on infinitesimal strain theory, while this shift arises from the rotational-magnetostrictive effect ($\delta = \delta R = 3[\lambda_{100} - \lambda_{111}] = 0.0008$) based on the finite strain theory [13–15,18]. Similarly, in the case of longitudinal waves (Fig. 3), this discrepancy is due to the lack of higher order corrections coming from morphic coefficients ($\delta = \delta G = |m_1^2|/C_{11} = 0.0005$) [15,18]. The low field regime below magnetic saturation is influenced by the Δs -effect due to domain wall displacement [14], and cannot be accounted for by the Simon effect described by function $S(H)$ in Table 3, as well as VelCrys, since they assume a magnetically saturated state [28,50]. In Fig. 5, we show the landscape of the fractional change in group velocity for the 3 types of waves (qP, qS1 and qS2) as a function of the ray direction (phase velocity direction) with applied magnetic field $\mu_0 H = (0, 0, 5)$ T generated with VelCrys. We see that for the qP wave we have $(v - v_0)/v_0 = 0$ at $k \parallel [001]$ consistent with the Simon effect ($S(H) = 0$), see Table 3. The largest value is observed in the qS1 wave about $(v - v_0)/v_0 = -450 \times 10^{-6}$. Note that the values shown in Fig. 5 do not include the Δs -effect. Theoretical expressions for other high symmetry ray and magnetic field directions were derived by Rouchy et al. [13,14], which can also be numerically studied with VelCrys since it allows any arbitrary direction of these quantities.

In addition to the ray direction $n = k/k$, the magnitude of the wavevector k can also influence the fractional change in group velocity due to exchange stiffness A . Recently, Korniienko et al. derived a more accurate expression for Simon effect [50] that includes such dependency. For instance, in the case of a qS1 wave with ray direction $k \parallel [001]$ and applied magnetic field $H \parallel [100]$, it reads [50]

$$S(H, k) = \frac{b_2^2}{2M_s C_{44}} \frac{\mu_0 \gamma^2 \left(H_K + \frac{2Ak^2}{\mu_0 M_s} + M_s + H_D + H \right)}{\left(k^2 \frac{C_{44}}{\rho} - \mu_0^2 \gamma^2 \left(H_K + \frac{2Ak^2}{\mu_0 M_s} + M_s + H_D + H \right)^2 \right)}, \quad (8)$$

where γ is the gyromagnetic ratio and the anisotropy field contains a component of magnetoelastic nature $H_K = \frac{1}{\mu_0 M_s} (2K_1 + \frac{2b_1^2}{C_{11} - C_{12}})$. At low k -values ($k \rightarrow 0$), Eq. (8) approaches the known formula given in Table 3. In Fig. 6, we show a comparison between Eq. (8) and the result obtained with VelCrys for an applied field $\mu_0 H = 8$ T. We observe that VelCrys gives a constant Simon effect as function of k , due to the lack of exchange stiffness in the current version of the program. Consequently, similar values to those given by Eq. (8) are only obtained at $ka_0/(2\pi) \lesssim 0.01$, where $a_0 = 3.749 \text{ \AA}$ is the lattice parameter [54], providing an estimation of the range of applicability of VelCrys with respect to k .

Fig. 5. Landscape of the fractional change in group velocity $(v - v_0)/v_0$ for the 3 types of waves (qP, qS1 and qS2) as a function of the ray direction (phase velocity direction) with applied magnetic field $\mu_0 \mathbf{H} = (0, 0, 5)$ T for cubic single crystals of disordered equiatomic Co-Pt alloy generated with VelCrys.

Fig. 6. Simon effect for the case of a qS1 wave with ray direction $\mathbf{k} \parallel [001]$, and applied magnetic field $\mu_0 H = 8$ T parallel to $[100]$. Red line and blue squares stand for Eq. (8) and VelCrys, respectively. Note that VelCrys computes the fractional change in group velocity $(v - v_0)/v_0$, so that we subtracted $(l - l_0)/l_0 = -\lambda_{100}/2$ from VelCrys data in order to get $S(H, k)$, according to Eqs. (5) and (6).

Table 4

Experimental elastic constants (C_{ij}), anisotropic magnetoelastic constants (b), magnetocrystalline anisotropy constants (K), saturation magnetization (M_s) and mass density (ρ) for hcp Co [59,60].

C_{ij}	(GPa)	b	(MPa)	K	(kJ/m ³)	$\mu_0 M_s$ (T)	ρ (kg/m ³)
C_{11}	307	b_{21}	-31.9	K_1	410	1.76	8900
C_{12}	165	b_{22}	25.5	K_2	150		
C_{13}	103	b_3	-8.1				
C_{33}	358	b_4	42.9				
C_{44}	75						

3.3. hcp Co

Most of the Co produced is used for special alloys [57]. A relatively large percentage of the world's production goes into magnetic alloys such as the Alnicos for permanent magnets. Sizable quantities are utilized for alloys that retain their properties at high temperatures and superalloys that are used near their melting points (where steels would become too soft). Co is also employed for hard-facing alloys, tool steels, low-expansion alloys (for glass-to-metal seals), and constant-modulus (elastic) alloys (for precision hairsprings). In this last example, we study magnetic corrections to group velocity for Co with hexagonal symmetry (hcp Co). We point out that the magnetic field effect on group velocity is still rather unexplored in hexagonal crystals [28,58]. The used parameters in VelCrys for this material are given in Table 4.

In Fig. 7, we computed the fractional change in group velocity for the qP wave with ray direction $\mathbf{k} \parallel [001]$ as a function of the applied

Fig. 7. (Top) Fractional change in group velocity $(v - v_0)/v_0$ for the qP wave with ray direction $\mathbf{k} \parallel [001]$ as a function of the applied magnetic field $\mathbf{H} \parallel [100]$ for hcp Co generated with VelCrys. (Bottom) The x and z components of direction cosines of equilibrium magnetization direction (α_x and α_z) as function of the applied magnetic field.

magnetic field $\mathbf{H} \parallel [100]$. At high fields ($\mu_0 H > 2$ T), we observe a field dependence $\sim 1/H$ consistent with the Simon effect. In the low field regime ($\mu_0 H < 2$ T), a non-monotonic behavior is observed probably due to an interplay between magnetic anisotropy, applied magnetic field, and rotation of magnetization. Similar peaks have been observed in Co-Pt alloys [14]. In Fig. 8, we present the landscape of the fractional change in group velocity for the 3 types of waves (qP, qS1 and qS2) as a function of the ray direction (phase velocity direction) with applied magnetic field $\mu_0 \mathbf{H} = (5, 0, 0)$ T generated with VelCrys. The highest values are found in the qS2 wave ($\Delta v/v_0 \sim -0.006$) along the direction of the magnetic field $\mathbf{k} \parallel \mathbf{H} \parallel [100]$. More theoretical analysis and experimental measurements in hexagonal crystals would be highly desirable to gain a deeper understanding of these results [58]. Note that the same limitations of the implemented methodology as in the case of cubic crystals (lack of higher order corrections and Δs -effect) are also expected for the hexagonal symmetry.

4. Impact

The web-based interactive tool VelCrys is dedicated to computing the group velocity of the acoustic waves in crystals for different directions of wave propagation, to account for the effects of an external magnetic field on sound and to plot 3D visualizations of studied effects. Potential applications of VelCrys could be in the research fields of geophysics [1-5], communication technology [6], biosensors [7], acoustic spin pumping [29], magnetization switching induced by sound waves [30-37], and picosecond ultrasonics [38]. VelCrys could also be useful for further post-processing of elastic tensor and magnetoelastic

Fig. 8. Landscape of the fractional change in group velocity $(v - v_0)/v_0$ for the 3 types of waves (qP, qS1 and qS2) as a function of the ray direction (phase velocity direction) with applied magnetic field $\mu_0 \mathbf{H} = (5, 0, 0)$ T for hcp Co generated with VelCrys.

constants obtained from automated schemes [42,43,61–63]. Moreover, its user-friendly web-based interface might be exploited in materials science-related databases [39,40].

5. Conclusion

In summary, we showed that the combination of Wang et al. [1] analytical solution of group velocity for a general elastic tensor with Rinaldi and Turilli [28] effective magnetic corrections could provide a convenient approach to easily compute the group velocity and fractional change in group velocity due to magnetic effects. This strategy has been implemented in the open source program VelCrys, facilitating the calculation of these quantities. VelCrys also includes visualization features to generate 3D plots of the landscape of these quantities as a function of the ray direction.

We have validated the program by recovering Wang et al. results of group velocity for the dry sandstone [1]. The magnetic corrections [28] were tested on cubic disordered Co-Pt alloy showing good agreement with theory and experiment after adding the Δs -effect [14]. We also applied this method to hcp Co finding a field dependence consistent with the Simon effect [17], as well as complex landscapes of fractional change in group velocity that have yet to be fully explained. The current version of the program has some limitations. For example, magnetic corrections to the elastic tensor have been implemented only for cubic I and hexagonal I symmetries. Moreover, the exchange stiffness was not included in the magnetic energy, as in the original work of Rinaldi and Turilli [28], which restricts its applicability to ultrasound waves with low $k a_0 / (2\pi) \lesssim 0.01$. Similarly, these corrections do not include higher order terms associated with morphic coefficients and rotational-magnetostrictive effect, as well as the Δs -effect related to domain wall displacement.

Lastly, the analysis of magnetic field was considered only in bulk magnetostrictive crystals. However, we point out that there are other systems where these kinds of studies might be also interesting. For example, magnetic films or multilayers are often coated on piezoelectric substrates to form Surface Acoustic Wave (SAW) and Bulk Acoustic Wave (BAW) devices for memory, magnetic-field sensors, and miniaturized antenna applications. In these applications, the ΔE (Young's modulus) effect and the ΔG (shear modulus) effect are of particular interest. Hopefully, these possible extensions and applications might be implemented in future versions of the program.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

P. Nieves: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **I. Kornienko:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **A. Fraile:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **J.M. Fernández-Díaz:** Validation, Resources, Investigation, Data curation. **R. Iglesias:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

D. Legut: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Source files of VelCrys tool are available on the GitHub repository [46].

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